

CoARA Action Plan 2024–2027

**Developing Responsible Research
and Researcher Assessment**

2024

1. Background

University of Eastern Finland's (UEF) [Strategy 2030](#) lays the basis of the responsible evaluation of research and researchers. According to the strategy, we seek solutions to global challenges in our profile areas through interdisciplinary research and interdisciplinary education. In this way, we will build a responsible and sustainable future. The university is an international, creative, participatory and inclusive scientific community that encourages open interaction and is guided by good scientific practice and sustainability. The university's strategic programmes for research and education include specific action plans for strategic development.

UEF's Steering Group for Research, led by the Rector of the University, has outlined principles for responsible research assessment and the use of research metrics in 2020. UEF follows the national and international recommendations for responsible researcher evaluation. Research and researcher assessment is primarily carried out by examining the scientific quality and content of research. The overall evaluation may also be supported by research metrics where relevant to the discipline of the researcher under evaluation. The objectives and criteria of the evaluation are openly available to all parties. The objectives and criteria are formulated in a way that is appropriate for both the individuals being evaluated and the research community.

At UEF, assessment situations and processes are diverse and support the conduct of scientifically high-quality research. Evaluation is carried out at all levels of the university, faculties, units, research communities and individual researchers. Evaluation is guided by university policies and guidelines and its practical implementation is based on relevance.

UEF is committed to the following recommendations, guidelines and policies in responsible research or researcher assessment. They provide the basis for developing the necessary processes and are part of daily management.

- [Action Programme for Sustainable Development and Responsibility](#) (UEF policy)
- [UEF Gender Equality and Equal Opportunities Plan](#) (UEF Policy)

- [University of Eastern Finland's Open Science and Research Policy](#) (UEF Policy)
- [Declaration on Open Science and Research](#) (national recommendation)
- [Good Practice in Researcher Evaluation](#) (national recommendation)
- Guidelines of the Finnish National Board on Research Integrity (TENK) on research integrity (RI) (national recommendation)
- CoARA, [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#) (EU Recommendation)
- [The Code of Conduct for Recruitment](#) (EU Recommendation)
- [DORA, The Declaration on Research Assessment](#) (international declaration)
- [HRS4R, HR Excellence in Research](#) (EU Recommendation)

According to the national recommendation on good practice in researcher evaluation in Finland (*Working group for responsible researcher evaluation: Good practice in researcher evaluation, 2020*), the general principles of researcher evaluation are transparency, integrity, equity, competence, and diversity.

UEF is actively involved in European-level and national networks and projects on responsible assessment. UEF is part of the university alliance YUFE (Young Universities for the Future of Europe) and actively contributed to its joint project, YUFERING. UEF was the leader in sub-tasks related to novel recognition of researchers, and Open Science within research assessment. Within the project, YUFE has jointly created a new template, YUFE Academic Assessment Portfolio, for the purpose of broadening the assessment of researchers. The portfolio resembles a narrative CV. The portfolio, filled by researchers who apply for academic positions, encompasses a wide array of academic tasks, including those related to research, teaching, teamwork, management, leadership, societal engagement, and outreach. Teaching and research staff at UEF were engaged in the testing of the portfolio. The portfolio was piloted within the MSCA selection process (YUFE4Postdocs), resulting in the recruitment of 51 postdocs to YUFE universities. In addition, UEF participates in GraspOS (Next Generation Research Assessment to Promote Open Science) project that supports the emerging policy reforms and creates an Open Science aware Responsible Research Assessment system. UEF is a member of the National Chapter of CoARA in Finland and participates actively in several national and European working

groups on responsible research assessment, e.g., via the Finnish National Open Science and Research Coordination (AVOTT) and the Young European Research Universities Network (YERUN) collaboration. University of Eastern Finland is a full member of European University Association (EUA) [Home \(eua.eu\)](https://eua.eu). Reforming academic career assessment is a strategic objective for EUA and one of the priorities for action outlined in 'Universities without walls - A vision for 2030'.

2. Principles for the responsible assessment of research and researchers

UEF's Steering Committee for Research decided to set up a working group on responsible assessment in 2022. The group includes experts from University Services and the Library, who have comprehensive knowledge of the university's research activities, administrative and support processes for research, the specificities of the faculties and the development of doctoral training at the university. The working group collected a review of the current state of assessment practices at UEF: when evaluation is carried out, who carries out the evaluation or is responsible for the process, and which documents guide the evaluation. Based on the review, UEF's Steering Committee for Research has confirmed principles for the responsible assessment of research and researchers at UEF.

The principles are based on UEF's strategy (justice, freedom, courage, transparency, responsibility, ethics and sustainability) and they draw on the commitments made by UEF and its own policies. The starting point for all assessment is that the process supports both the researcher and the university, with scientific quality and impact at its core. The evaluation will consider the open access to research data and results and the ethics of the research. Research outputs and the impact of the researcher's activities will be assessed as a whole. Peer review can also be supported by the responsible use of research metrics, considering the specificities of the disciplines.

Our evaluation practices support responsible recruitment and career transparency. The diversity of research inputs and careers is recognized. Practices that promote open, transparent and inclusive research and ensure equality and equal treatment are also essential.

The CoARA Agreement on reforming research assessment contains principles for overarching conditions. They include descriptions connected to complying with ethical and integrity rules and practices and their highest priority, the freedom of scientific research, autonomy of research organizations, as well as the independence and transparency of the data, research infrastructure and criteria necessary for research assessment and for determining research impacts. These principles are at the core of the implementation of the reform also at UEF.

3. Focus areas and activities related to the responsible assessment of research and researchers

UEF's Steering Group for Research, led by the Rector of the University, decided to focus the reform activities especially on **the university's recruitment processes** including all the academic career stages. The work on reforming the assessment methods will become a natural part of the university's current **career modelling work**. To support the researchers' job planning and career progression, practices such as **researcher performance appraisal discussions** will be developed and appraisal practices in **salary evaluation** will be updated. The need for reform will also be considered in **UEF's research assessment exercise (UEFRAE)** processes and principles.

Academic **recruitment** is an essential part of UEF's strategy, and their success will strengthen our performance and support renewal and effectiveness. Recruitment methods include open, direct and proactive recruitment. Most basic university posts are filled through open recruitment. For short project-type posts both open recruitment and direct recruitment are used. According to the Universities Act, the post of Professor may be filled by invitation without an open call when a professionally distinguished person may be invited to take the post, or a

person is appointed for a fixed period to the post. Only a person who indisputably fulfils the qualification requirements may be appointed to the post by invitation. In direct recruitment, a candidate is known to represent the profile and best skills to be sought directly and the person's skills are evaluated to be sufficient for the post. Proactive recruitment is the process of getting to know and collaborating with research groups and researchers whose research interests best match the competences sought. The aim is to recognize candidates with competence and suitability for future recruitment needs, as well as to raise awareness of the University's research and other activities. All recruitment procedures are based on commitments listed in the first chapter of this document. Priority areas for development include the development of impact evaluation, recruitment-related communication, the compilation and dissemination of guidance on responsible evaluation, and the development of qualitative evaluation in national and international cooperation.

The versatile career paths and opportunities offered by UEF are available to the entire university staff. The academic career model is based on the four-stage career model that progresses through degrees and merits. The four-stage career model and its nomenclature are complemented by the tenure track and UEF Teacher career model. The career stages on the tenure track are assistant professor and associate professor before professorship. In practice, only a limited number of the most accomplished researchers, who are considered to have the prerequisites to advance to the tenured professor level, will be accepted into the tenure track system. As a rule, all positions in the academic career model include research and teaching. The work on the career model at our university is continuous and proactive. Current goals include identifying needs for new roles and combinations at the interfaces of position structures that are commonly used at universities, searching for new operating models to support the careers of doctoral researchers and project staff, and increasing and supporting students' awareness of academic careers. UEF is involved in international development projects and networks that seek solutions to challenges related to research careers and, together with other European universities, develop the status of researchers, academic careers and responsible evaluation of researchers and research.

UEF actively supports the careers of all its teaching and research staff, for instance by offering training related to research management, university pedagogy, and transversal skills. The current work on career models will be continued, with the actions listed in Table 1 as specific areas for development.

UEF has performed **research assessment exercises (UEFRAE)** every 5-6 years since 2009. Assessment is done by external independent evaluators from various research fields. UEFRAE process is to evaluate UEF's research activities, and the results of the assessment have always been and will continue to be used in strategy work. Several strategic development actions have raised from the recommendations of the UEFRAE processes. RAE processes in Finland are not guided by any external parties, and there are no national guidelines. UEFRAE processes are led by the Rector responsible for research, and the principles of UEFRAE are determined by the steering group for UEFRAE processes. In the recent evaluations, the criteria of assessment have been A) Research excellence and scientific quality, B) Research environment and operational conditions, C) Impact beyond academia and D) Strategic visions and implementation. The University will continue to develop the evaluation of research by developing the activities listed in Table 1.

UEF recognizes **performance appraisal discussions** as important processes for assessing the work contributions of researchers; they serve as a platform for acknowledging work accomplishments and for setting future goals. Especially for early-stage researchers, they are occasions for gaining feedback on one's work, and help researchers identify their strengths and areas for improvement (incl. needs for additional training). Appraisals also provide a platform for discussing individual long-term career goals, incl. future employment opportunities for those working on a fixed-term contract. Appraisals are also a place for ensuring that the researchers' research goals align with the broader objectives of their institution/unit/research group.

UEF has based **salary assessments** on qualitative judgements. As a part of general collective agreement for universities, salaries are based on the requirement level of the duties and on personal performance. The aim of the salary system for Finnish universities is, for instance, to support the staff and the enhancement of their skills in seeking more demanding positions, but also to develop and improve supervisory work and management. The system in use influences promotion practices or rewards, in particular, but also recruitment. The assessment of the job-related salary element is based on written, qualitative descriptions of the job's content. The interaction skills and knowledge required for the position are considered in addition to the nature and responsibilities of the post. A peer assessment of the correct salary level is carried out via the leaders' estimations and evaluation group discussions where peers (staff's representatives) from labour unions participate in the assessments with the employer's representatives. The principal evaluation factors in the evaluation system for the personal salary element for teaching and research staff are pedagogical merits, research merits, merits in societal activities and in open science, as well university community merits.

Table 1. UEF's focused actions for developing, reforming and monitoring the responsible researcher and research evaluation 2024–2027.

Developing evaluation for recruitments – Actions	
Interactions for development	<p>Continuing to develop overall assessment incl. qualitative criteria for impact evaluation, considering the working life knowledge needs and the objectives of society and stakeholders</p> <p>Ensuring interdisciplinary dialogue in the development of assessment methods</p>
Communication	<p>Continuing to develop recruitment communication through internal and external channels and by using a variety of communication tools</p> <p>Developing communication on the implementation, scheduling and evaluation of recruitments under the strategy programmes at the university</p>
Leadership	<p>Emphasize the university leadership's commitment to the responsible researcher and research evaluation in recruitment communication</p> <p>Continuing the strategic and proactive human resources planning and its implementation as a basis for recruitment.</p> <p>Maintaining the identification and confirmation of strategic research profile and focus areas as a basis for recruitment assessments</p> <p>Monitoring the implementation of the reform of responsible evaluation and providing further guidance where necessary</p>
Processes and tools	<p>Updating the guidelines for responsible evaluation principles, criteria and methods in diverse recruitment situations.</p> <p>Developing guidelines directed at internal and external evaluators about the principles of responsible evaluation at UEF, including joint tasks with other organizations</p> <p>Continuing to develop instructions for applicants/recruits about qualitative evaluation and self-evaluation including advanced methods to show competence in different tasks/disciplines</p> <p>The university considers the promotion of open science, research, and teaching as part of the career models and recruitment processes</p>

Developing academic careers – Actions

Interactions for development

National and international recommendations and guidelines are followed and considered in the university's own career model work and connected evaluation processes

Continuing stakeholder collaboration in academic career development

Communication

Developing career communication, incl. evaluation processes connected to the career opportunities, in the context of the diversity of research careers.

Leadership

Promoting the career model work at the university in proactive way

Continuing to identify new roles and tasks at the interfaces of position structures that are commonly used at universities. Developing of evaluation methods is involved in the process.

Processes and tools

UEF promotes and monitors the working conditions of different staff groups according to a diversity plan, which is updated regularly

UEF's doctoral education will be reformed, including doctoral education pilots and support for post-doctoral careers. This will include a reform of the evaluation process and content.

The guidelines for teaching assessment will be harmonized and the assessment process will be updated at the university

In accordance with UEF's strategy, activities promoting open science, open access publishing, opening of research data and methods, and the production and opening of education and educational resources, as well as the promotion of an open operating principle, will be considered advantageous in the evaluation (in academic career progression)

Research Assessment – Actions

Interactions for development

Continuing the development of the use of qualitative indicators in research assessment and how qualitative research outputs are measured and recorded at UEF

Continuing the development of the responsible use of research metrics

Broadening the research assessment focuses (focus not only on scientific excellence)

Communication

The diversity of research outputs and their equal contribution in assessment is clarified for researchers and evaluators

Leadership

University leadership is committed to the principles of responsible assessment when setting up evaluation guidelines at UEF

Processes and tools

UEFRAE ensures independent, open and transparent assessment. Assessment is done by independent evaluators representing the fields under evaluation. Guidelines are published before evaluation. Units under evaluation make also self-assessment reports.

University provides data for various assessment processes (UEFRAE, university rankings etc.) in a transparent and similar manner

In the assessment processes the UEF promotes openness. The evaluation processes and results will be made openly available in UEF eRepository.

Researcher activity support: Performance appraisal discussions and salary assessment-

Actions

Interactions for development

Continuing to emphasize the need to hold performance appraisal discussions on a regular basis to support the transparency career advancement, and to improve knowledge of the evaluation policy and processes

Continuing to have a transparent salary assessment process both at the start of the employment contract and during the contract (entailing the job-related salary element based on the requirements of the duties and personal performance). Conducting transparent salary reviews based on gender to avoid biases.

Communication

Continuing to develop communication on performance appraisal discussions.

Leadership

Enabling the researchers to provide a description of the objective, significance and effectiveness of their own research. Providing feedback on the researcher's career plan by identifying diverse competences, achievements, and future career goals, and needs for improvement.

Processes and tools

Review needs for updating university-level performance appraisal discussion templates to fully recognize the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research

The work done to improve the openness of research, research data and methods, publishing, education, and educational resources is valued in the criteria for merits and in the planning of work tasks